

IRRIGATED-RAINFED RICE AREA MAPPING WITH CLIMATIC PARAMETERS OVER BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT: Spatial information on irrigated area is very important for crops water requirements, agricultural planning, water management, and climate changes. It is challenging to map irrigated rice areas by images classification methods due to the spectral similarity between with and without irrigation. In this study, we developed an index for potential irrigated rice area map for three different seasons by using remote sensing-based evapotranspiration (MOD16A2) and precipitation (GSMaP) data from 2003-2016. In this index, the crop evapotranspiration is higher than the effective precipitation in a region is considered as irrigated area. Along with this, the land use and land cover (MOD12CQ) data used for agricultural area extraction. Further, the result compared with the National statistical and others relevant irrigated area data. The result shows the great variation of irrigated rice area among the rice cultivating season and climatic variables. The dry season irrigated rice (Boro) area shows a good relationship with the national statistical data, but the wet seasons irrigated rice areas shows a great deviation. Results from this study suggest that our method is a promising tool for mapping irrigated rice area especially for the dry season.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Bangladesh is an agricultural country with a very high cropping intensity and diversity. The rice is the dominant crop of the country and it covers three-fourths of all cropland area and contributes 70% of calories consumed (Majumder et al. 2016). Due to the drastic population growth (98 billion) growth, the country needs to produce 70% more food (FAOSTAT, 2015) in 2050. But the arable land area of the country is even decreasing over time due to increasing demand for residential and industrial use (Hasan et al., 2013). The rice cultivated areas of Bangladesh is located low, flat and inundated areas and these areas are easily damaged by natural disaster likes floods, drought and storms. Currently, agriculture consumes more than 84% of the withdrawal groundwater (FAO, 2010). As a result, accurate information on irrigation extent, irrigation requirement and impacts of irrigation on environment are very important. The long-term phenology analysis, soil moisture and temperature analysis and the various indices analysis based remote sensing studies are becoming popular for irrigated area mapping. The global map of irrigated areas version 5 (GIMA5) used census-based statistics and produced irrigation equipped area with resolution of 5 arc-minutes from 2000 to 2008 (Siebert et al., 2005). The MIRCA 2000 (Portmann et al., 2010) also produced same data set on 2000. The GIMA (Thenkabail et al., 2009) used 500m remote sensing data and unsupervised classifier is the higher resolution map for world irrigation area. The Global Rain-fed, Irrigated, and Paddy Croplands (GRIPC) map (Salmon et al., 2015) has the highest spatial resolution (500 m) among these four

products. These global studies are global scale and not effective for the local scale studies. These global data set does not represent the accurate irrigation data because the cropping pattern and irrigated area changing over the time. There are also a number of studies on local level, MODIS 500 m Spectral Matching Method in India (Dheeravath, v., Thenkabail, P.S., et al., 2010)), crop types and irrigation water use (Salman, J. M. et al. 2015). Most of the study are- phenology based, spectral matching, and spatial distribution. Moreover, there is very less significant irrigated area studies with remote sensing in Bangladesh.

1.2 Objectives

This study is an attempt to irrigated area mapping with RS based climatic data over Bangladesh. The objectives of the studies are-

- (i) To mapping rice and non-rice area,
- (ii) To assess the irrigated and rainfed rice area with seasonal variation,
- (iii) Comparison with relevant source of information.

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data

The MOD13A2 NDVI data with Kalman's filtered and MOD12Q1 LULC data have been used for rice area mapping. The MOD16A2 data are used for Potential Evapotranspiration analysis. The global satellite mapping of precipitation (GSMaP) data used for effective precipitation calculation. The auxiliary and validation data have been collected from Bangladesh bureau of statistics (BBS), Bangladesh meteorological department (BMD), Bangladesh agriculture research council (BARC),

IRRI, CSIRO, FAO and relevant literature review from Journals and publications.

2.2 Rice Area Mapping

The rice and non-rice area mapping are an important stage of this study. The MOD16A2 NDVI data with Kalman filtered in 1km spatial and 16 days temporal resolution used as the main data source. The MOD12Q1 LULC data reclassified and extracted the agricultural area in Bangladesh. Then, the MOD_NDVI data masked the agricultural area and distinguish the agricultural land of Bangladesh. The BRRRI crop calendar used for rice growing season determination. More than 700 ROI's for each year selected for spectral signature extraction and then used maximum likelihood classifier (MLC) used for rice area identification. In figure-1 shows the spectral signature classes of rice. The three different rice growing season are mapped as- *Boro*, *Aus*, and *Amon* rice area.

Figure-1: Annual Spectral variation of rice

2.3 Irrigated Area Mapping

The irrigated area has been calculated by using the effective precipitation and evapotranspiration. The monthly GSMaP spatial resolution downscaled into 1km and used for effective precipitation. The FAO guided equation have been modified as follow;

$$E_p = (T_p - 5) \times 0.75 \dots\dots\dots (Eq-1)$$

Where, E_p is the effective precipitation, T_p total precipitation. The crop water requirement for rice calculated from MOD_ET data and crop coefficient (K_c), the K_c value for rice growing stages used from the reference data.

$$R_{CWR} = MOD_{ET} \times K_c \dots\dots\dots (Eq-2)$$

Where, R_{CWR} is the rice crop water requirement, MOD_{ET} is monthly evapotranspiration and K is crop coefficient.

The rice is cultivated under flooded condition and the sources of waters are naturally by precipitation or artificially by irrigation. So, the pixel-based composition of MOD_ET based crop water requirement and GSMaP effective precipitation used for irrigated area determination. If the crop water requirement is higher than the effective precipitation, the pixel considered as the irrigated area and lower means the rainfed area (Islam and Takeuchi, 2018). The equation is as follows:

$$R_{CWR} > E_p = \text{Irrigated and} \\ R_{CWR} \leq E_p = \text{Rainfed} \dots\dots\dots (Eq-3)$$

On the base of Eq-3, the irrigated and rainfed area mapped. In between the irrigated and rainfed area there is set a range value (± 20) with rice water stress tolerable and considered as supplementary irrigated area. This

irrigated and rainfed area map compose with the rice area map and finally calculated the irrigated and rainfed rice area. The three different seasons irrigated and rainfed rice area are calculated according to the crop calendar. The irrigated and rainfed rice area data are compared with the Bangladesh bureau of statistics data and FAO data. The data are statistically analysed and represent with the graphs, figure and table. The overall flow chart of research methodology shown in fig.-2.

Figure-2: Flow Chart of the research methodology

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Rice Area Map

The rice area mapping is important for the irrigated-rainfed rice area mapping. The main three season rice in Bangladesh-i) *Boro* rice: dry and almost rainless season from December to March ii) *Aus*: wet and rainy season from April to July and iii) *Amon*: mixed wet and dry season from August to November. The three different season rice area are mapped and calculated the area. The Amon rice area is dominant and decreasing from 5.07 million ha in 2003 to 4.50 million ha in 2016. Although the favourable condition the Amon rice area decreasing due to the less per unit yield (2.1 tone/ha). The dry season Bor rice area increasing day by day from 3.39 million ha in 2003 to 4.86 million ha in 2016 in the study area. The high cost and fully irrigated Boro rice area increased due to the high per unit yield (3.78 tone/ha) and less disaster risk. The rainy season Aus rice area decreasing significantly in the study area. In figure-3 shows the area of different rice area in Bangladesh

Seasonal Rice Area of Bangladesh from 2003-2016

Figure-3: Seasonal Rice Area Map of Bangladesh

3.2 Irrigated Rice Area Map

The irrigated area mapping over Bangladesh is the most challenging due to the heterogonies cropping pattern, high cropping intensity and the fragmentation of farm size. In Bangladesh, cropping pattern follows the weather pattern and the natural calamities. During the dry and rainless season from December to March is less hazardous and good for the Rice production. Although, rice is produced under the flooded condition but due to the less natural hazard risk, most of the rice produced in this season. During this season the monthly precipitation rate is very low, almost rainless and temperature is also getting high and the evapotranspiration rate is also very high. As a result, the irrigated area over Bangladesh during this season almost fully irrigated. The irrigated map on December to march shows almost all over of the country is irrigated. In figure-4(a) and 4 (b) shown the irrigated area of Bangladesh.

Figure- 4(a): Irrigated rice area of Bangladesh

Figure- 4(b): Map of the Irrigated area of Bangladesh

3.3 Data Validation

3.3.1 Precipitation Data: The Global satellite mapping of precipitation (GSMaP) data used for the irrigated area mapping over Bangladesh. The precipitation data compared with the weather station wise observed precipitation data from Bangladesh meteorological department. It's shows a very good agreement in the less precipitated month like December to February but during the monsoon season the data follows the same pattern but under estimated then the observed data. As a result, due to the under estimated of monthly precipitation from the GSMaP data didn't affected the irrigated area that's much. In the figure-5 shows the regression of precipitation from GSMaP and Meteorological (BMD, 2003-2016) data.

Figure-5: Regression of GSMaP and observed data

3.3.2 Evapotranspiration: The crop water requirement depends on the evapotranspiration of the crop area. In this study, the rice crop water requirement has been calculated from MOD16A2 evapotranspiration data and the crop coefficient. The evapotranspiration data from Bangladesh meteorological department weather data and Penman–Monteith formula used reference evapotranspiration data of Bangladesh (Rahman, 2018). The reference ET data and the MOD_ET data has been compared over Bangladesh. The result shows that the MOD_ET follows a very good agreement with the reference ET data. During the dry season (November to February) shows a very good agreement but in the rainy season (April- August) shows the overestimated than the reference ET data. The MOD_ET data over Bangladesh in October shows very high over estimated. As a result, the Amon irrigated area affected. The evapotranspiration data and crop coefficient value from reference data used in this study. The regression of MOD_ET and reference ET shows in figure-6

Figure-6: Regression of MOD_ET and reference ET

3.4 Accuracy Assessment

3.4.1 Rice Area Map: The calculated rice area compared with the statistical data from Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS, 2001-2017). The calculated Boro rice area and the statistically Boro rice shows a very good agreement with statistical data. The Amon rice shows the under estimation to the statistical data. The Aus rice area has an overestimation than the statistical Aus rice area. The dry season rice has a good agreement with the statistical data, but the wet season rice has a low agreement with the statistical data. In figure- 7 shows the comparison of calculated and statistical rice area of Bangladesh.

Figure-7. Comparison of calculated rice area.

3.4.2 Irrigated Rice Area: The irrigated rice area of Bangladesh has been calculated using the climatic parameter; evapotranspiration and effective precipitation. So, the irrigated area depends on the climatic condition of the season or year. The calculated rice area fluctuated with the weather condition of the year. The Boro rice area has a very good relationship with the statistical data. Due to the very high difference between the effective precipitation and crop water requirement, the irrigated Boro rice area calculation has a very good agreement. The Aus rice area considered as the rainfed rice growing season and irrigated aus rice area not available. As a result, the irrigated Aus rice area hasn't compared with the statistical data. The comparison of calculated irrigated rice area and statistical data shows in figure- 8.

Figure-8: Calculated and statistical irrigated area

4. CONCLUSION

The irrigated rice area mapping over Bangladesh is challenging due to the heterogenic cropping pattern and fragmented farm size. The aimed of this study to calculate the irrigated area with long-term and seasonal variation aspects. The result shows a very good agreement to the national statistical data in dry but very poor agreement in mixed Amon and Aus rice growing season. The model used for this study for irrigated and rainfed rice area mapping could be a useful tool for irrigated rice area mapping with climatic parameter. For the further study, analysis the Amon and Aus rice irrigated area for increasing the accuracy in Bangladesh.

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